

From growth to silence: expressive endeavours at the end of life

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ABSTRACT

This ethnographic study explores how severely ill and dying persons participating in expressive forms of culture, such as art, blogging and talking, confront dying and death. Influenced by the increasing relevance of values such as expressivity and creativity and the mediatization of everyday life, more and more people facing death in globalised Western culture seek their own expressive ways to deal with finitude in online and offline contexts. Framed by Tony Walter's sociology of death, which captures key features of death attitudes within Western societies, this study identifies commonalities in the different expressive endeavours at the end of life. The data for the analysis stem from encounters with 12 persons receiving palliative care in Switzerland. The study found that the performances of individualistic expressivity are informed by the idea of personal growth, prosumer and sharing culture, a quest for belonging and the wish for silence. The findings aim to contribute to further the understanding of current forms of mediated dying in networked society.

KEYWORDS

Art and expression;
blogging; digital coping;
digital prosumerism;
individualism; palliative care;
Walter's ideal types of death

Introduction

I have to say goodbye to everything, my whole life comes to an end. Right? That's why I talk about my life and my work with you, as well as the pastor and the psychologist. I feel the urge to once more talk about my life, my experiences, my education, encounters with other people and so on. [...]. When I look back at this week, here in the palliative care ward, I realise that I've really had the urge to talk. Also, to you.

This quote is from Remo, a deacon and one of the 12 persons I met during my ethnographic research 2020–2021 in palliative care units, hospices and personal surroundings.¹ The emotional intensity of his words has left a mark on me and is retrospectively characteristic of the overall mood of my conversations and encounters with severely ill and dying people. This urge to talk about life in the face of death, to express emotions, and to keep oneself, the presence and the past alive through the exchange of thoughts and imagery is a common feature of the cases I was able to study. Nurtured by the therapeutic culture of palliative care, which promotes open awareness and acceptance of death (Hart et al., 1998; Saake et al., 2019), and stimulated by the mediatization of everyday

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life, the participants used a variety of media and practices to process the experience of dying. As in other recent studies of persons living with terminal illness (Butters, 2021; Irving, 2017), I observed that alongside the expressive capacity of words, art and photography were important forms of communication to convey experiences and make meaningful connections in the difficult situation. In this article, I use the term 'expressive endeavours' to capture my interlocuters' participation in expressive forms of culture at the end of life. The aim of this study is to explore these endeavours and to identify commonalities in them. Different forms of verbal and artistic representation of the experience of illness emerged in the conversations and encounters and I decided in the course of the analytical process of the research to subsume them under the aforementioned term. The term covers a number of things such as artistic projects pursued in the hospital and writing about illness on blogging sites on the web as well as therapeutic conversation with professionals and peers. The term is deliberately defined broadly in order to capture different qualities and aspects of 'being expressive' at the end of life, using the expressive capacity of spoken words and visual art as well as the communicative potentials of the Internet. While the anthropology of dying (Kellehear, 2015; Lawton, 2000; Menzfeld, 2018) and phenomena such as blogging of terminally ill patients (Andersson, 2019; Caduff, 2022; Lagerkvist & Andersson, 2017; Recuber, 2017) have gained growing attention, few studies have investigated how dying persons use a variety of means to confront their illness and mortality. Maija Butters (2021) highlights the importance of photos, artwork and blogs to explore how patients perceive their illness. Additionally, Andrew Irving (2017) reminds us that art, in particular, can provide an important resource to express emotional intensity in dying when pain or phases of illness 'undermine language and produce an unbridgeable gap between signified and signifier' (p. 122).²

The ethnographic record I present in this article is based on encounters and conversations with seven women and five men receiving palliative care in Switzerland. They suffered predominantly from cancer and experienced long dying trajectories up to several years. Dying is a social, psychological and biological process (Glaser & Strauss, 1974) which may not be limited to a few days or hours before death, but can begin when, for example, a terminal illness is diagnosed (Kellehear, 2017). Some of the participants died just a couple of days after I met them, other are still alive. Their ages ranged from forty-eight to one-hundred-and-one years old. They engaged in different lifestyle behaviours and had both religious and secular identities, yet they all belonged to the white middle classes, were well educated and seemed to share the desire to communicate their experiences of illness. To frame their narratives, practices and negotiations of illness broadly, I introduce Tony Walter's (1994) sociology of death as an analytical tool in this article. In his book *The Revival of Death*, Walter sketches three ideal types of death: 'traditional death', 'modern death' and 'neo-modern death' (p. 48) (Figure 1). The different dimensions of the three types can be considered as a 'compass' which provides information about the responses to death that western societies have been prone to over time. Walter's ideal types illustrate, for example, that modern death fosters emotional privacy whereas neo-modern death, as cultivated by hospice and palliative care, values conversation and encourages the expression of experiences and emotions. Further, the ideal types capture the social context and structure which frame death attitudes. Generally speaking, traditional death is connected to community belonging, whereas neo-modern death, in contrast, is built on personal identity and

48 Doing it my way

Table 4.1 Three types of death

	<i>Traditional</i>	<i>Modern</i>	<i>Neo-modern</i>
Bodily context			
1 Archetypal death	Plague	Cancer/coronary	Cancer/AIDS
2 Dying trajectory	Fast	Hidden	Prolonged
3 Life expectancy	40	70	80
4 See others dying	Frequently	Rarely	Witness dying not death
5 Human condition	Living with death	Death controlled	Living with dying
6 Typical death	Child	Elderly	Elderly
7 Social birth	Follows physical birth	At physical birth	Precedes physical birth
Social death	Follows physical death	Precedes physical death	At physical death
8 Untypical death	Old (venerated)	Young (senseless)	Young (senseless)
Social context			
9 Social structure	Community	Public vs. private	Private and public intertwined
10 Personhood Found in	Belonging Community	Identity Family	Identities Relationships
Death = loss of	Social position	Identity	Identities
Task post death	Reconstruct roles	Reconstruct identity	Reconstruct identities
Done through	Mourning	Grief	Grief work
Authority			
11 Authority	God/Tradition	Medical expertise	Self
Known through	The will of God	Doctor's orders	I did it my way
12 Institution	Clergy (male)	Doctor (male)	Counsellor (female)
13 Meaning	Church	Hospital	Home/hospice
	Given	Abolished (in public)	Created interpersonally
14 Religion	Given	Choice of church	Inner spirituality
Coping			
15 Courage shown in	Prayer	Silence	Talk
16 Coping strategy	Ritual	Emotional privacy	Expressing
17 Lay support	Neighbours/Kin	Nuclear family	Self-help groups
18 Surveillance by of	Priest/Neighbour	Doctor/Neighbour	Counsellor
	Soul/Behaviour	Body/Behaviour	Feelings
The journey			
19 Traveller	Soul	Body	Psyche
20 Death	Result of sin	Caused naturally	Inner journey
21 Mode of transport	Ritual action	Technology/Drugs	Talk
22 Funeral	Burial	Cremation	Life-centred
Organised by	Community	Commerce/Municipality	Memorial society/DIY
Values			
23 Values	Respect	Health/Privacy/Dignity/fighting	Emotion/Growth/Choice
24 Worst sins	Unbelief	Independence	Autonomy/Control
25 The good death	Conscious	Intrusion	Isolation/Denial
	Ready to meet Maker	Unconscious/Sudden	Aware/Precious/My way
		No bother to others	Finish business

Figure 1. Ideal types of death. In: Walter, T. (1994). *The revival of death*, p. 48.

relationships. However, ideal types and empirical reality are not congruent. Ideal types should be used as a guide to understand ‘the exact composition of the colours that actually exist’ (Walter, 1994, p. 49). This study sheds empirical light on Walter’s ideal types drawing on my encounters and conversations with persons facing severe illness thus refining the concept of neo-modern death based on the findings.

The ‘expressive revolution’

Dying and death as cultural phenomena have always been subject to social and religious changes that influence practices to deal with illness, finitude and transcendence. In recent centuries, individualism altered human attempts to cope with existential issues in the West. Generally speaking, with the beginning of the Renaissance period and the rise of humanistic values death became more and more an individual affair and concern (Ariès, 1976, 2008). This development intensified through incipient modernisation in which the importance of overarching moral and religious systems declined due to social differentiation, thus permitting individuals to cope with dying and death according to their lifestyle and needs. However, as Allan Kellehear (2007) argues, the individual freedom and ‘the pressure to “make sense” of the world’ (p. 137) are not confined to modern populations but ‘have been those of all urban – indeed “urbane” – populations since the birth of cities and the middle classes serving them’ (ibid.). Yet a rather new development that is appearing in the approach to death in these populations from 1960 onwards is that of ‘expressive individualism’. Expressive individualism ‘holds that each person has a unique core of feeling and intuition that should unfold or be expressed if individuality is to be realised’ (Bellah et al., 1996, p. 340). In the course of this development, numerous therapies and practices developed which ‘promise to help you find yourself, realise yourself, release your true self, and so on’ (Taylor, 2007, p. 475). This culture is also reflected in hospice philosophy which emerged in the 1960s and 70s and provided an approach to terminal care adapted to the requirements of individualised and secularised Protestant culture (Clark, 1998; Metzger, 2023a; Nash, 2013). In the context of hospice and palliative care, self-understanding, self-transcendence and self-discovery through means such as conversation and art are promoted to find existential comfort at the end of life (Saunders, 2003). As Walter (1994) highlights, in ‘neo-modern death’, the journey of dying becomes a ‘journey of the self’ (p. 58). In this journey, which today takes place in different social contexts (at home, in hospitals, on the Internet etc.) and is mediated by aesthetics as well as by rituals and medicine (Butters, 2021), tasks such as ‘finishing business’ or spiritual development can be accomplished, depending on the needs and lifestyle of the patient.

More recently, the ‘expressive revolution’, which took place mainly among middle class people and affected the way this group copes with dying and death (Walter, 1994), has also become manifest on the Internet. The widespread public display of a patient’s intimate life in social media and blogs can be seen as a clear indicator of this global trend (see e.g. Andersson, 2019; Caduff, 2022; Metzger, 2023b; Recuber, 2017). According to Yvonne Andersson (2019), the public revealing of intimacies on the Internet counteracts modernity’s sequestration of death and draws attention to ‘existential givens and insecurities, such as illness and death’ (p. 15). ‘Digital affect cultures’ (Döveling et al., 2018, p. 1), which foster emotional exchange and give rise to feelings of belonging, have

become important social spaces for coping with adversity and hardship. Experiences and emotions attached to illness and existential issues emerging in these spaces 'can be seen as the outcome of particular relational configurations, or "relational scenarios"' (2018, p. 2). Furthermore, dying and death have been given public visibility in recent years through art and artistic practices (Macho, 2007). Terminally ill artists display their experience of illness and suffering in videos, diaries and autobiographies. Corina Caduff (2022) argues that these pieces express 'the wish for self-determination', 'the strive for recognition', 'the urge to communicate' and the aim to 'create a legacy' or 'break the taboo of death' (p. 7, own translation). Overall, the appreciation of artistic lifestyles and creativity in (late) modern Western societies (Reckwitz, 2017) combined with the mediatisation of everyday life and the individualistic philosophy of hospice and palliative care (see e.g. Metzger, 2023b; Randall & Downie, 2006; Thoresen, 2003) contribute to an expressive culture of dying and death which values expression of and talk about feelings.

As we will see, my interlocuters participate in this culture in various way, sharing forms of behaviour and values alongside their individual ways to come to terms with finitude and non-being.

Methods and data

(Digital) ethnography

I chose an open and process-oriented ethnographic approach, which also accounts for the digital and acknowledges 'the ways in which media are inseparable from the other activities, technologies, materialities and feelings through which they are used, experienced and operate' (Pink et al., 2016, p. 9), to explore people's experiences of illness and their responses to death. My interest in media developed many years ago while I was training as a photographer in art school before I leaped on an academic path. As I had no previous personal and professional experience with persons facing serious illness and death, I did not have a particular research question in mind when I started field research and to collect data. My primary aim was to be sensitive to the realities and situations of the persons, discovering interesting themes in the iterative process between data collection and analysis. The open and process-oriented approach should also allow for adapting to the difficult living conditions of the participants and actively involve them in the research process according to their needs and health condition. Ethnographic research is not based on a distanced observational stance but is an inevitably collaborative activity (Pink et al., 2016). From March 2020 to September 2021, I made several short field visits to palliative care stations, hospices and the participants' personal surroundings. The participants were recruited from four different institutions (three urban hospitals and a hospice in a rural area in the Swiss mountains) and a palliative care outpatient service. Due to their poor health and need for privacy and retreat, it was difficult to follow them closely over a longer period of time. Further, my research was complicated by the COVID-19 crisis. In times of lockdowns, field access was hindered and I had to communicate with some participants via video conferencing, email or WhatsApp. The study is comprised of several 'short-term ethnographies' in which the ethnographer clearly indicates his intentions and engages participants in his/her project (Pink & Morgan, 2013). Pink and Morgan argue that short-term ethnographies are by no means 'quick and dirty' or less valuable than long-

term engagement, but 'go beyond observation' (p. 353) to create encounters which benefit from the production of forms of intensity and empathy. After potential participants were recommended to me by doctors or nurses, I asked the persons personally to engage in my project. I told them at our first encounter that I take an interest in their person, situation and the way they deal with existential issues. In addition, I indicated that they might want to share with me what concerns and moves them the most at this difficult moment in life. Starting with these informal conversations, I deepened my understanding of their experiences and perspectives with in-depth interviews, photo-elicitation (Lapenta, 2011) and internet-ethnography.

Data collection

In this article, I draw on different types of data: 1) eight in-depth interviews with a maximum length of two hours, which were recorded on a digital audio recorder and subsequently transcribed. Quotations in this article were translated from Swiss German to English and therefore do not reflect all original nuances and subtleties; 2) one photo-elicitation interview which was conducted and recorded on the video conferencing platform Zoom and subsequently transcribed; 3) Facebook postings, containing photographs, video and text messages of one of the participants; 4) field notes of participant observation and informal chats; 5) e-mail conversations with enquiries on topics raised in the interviews.

Data analysis

I used an open coding approach to analyse the data. For ethnographic studies, working from the 'ground up' is a beneficial strategy, which has been, for example, demonstrated in grounded theory research (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Overall, my analytical path was framed by Walter's (1994) ideal types of death. After conducting a preliminary analysis, which identified different performances of expressivity in the sample, I assigned codes to the data, each code representing a concept of potential interest. The insights I gained allowed me to illuminate the key aim of this study, i.e. to identify commonalities in the participants' expressive endeavours at the end of life. The analysis is organised according to three themes which synthesise these common traits: 1) mundane and spiritual forms of growth and transcendence; 2) self-empowerment and the spirit of sharing; 3) voices of silence.

Analysis

Mundane and spiritual forms of growth and transcendence

Ongoing project realisation, exercise and conversation to attain happiness, immortality, purity or perfection was a salient theme in the observed cases. The participants' strive for growth had both an extrinsic and intrinsic orientation and was driven by secular values in one case and religiously motivated in the other. The analysis revealed that they put effort into personal goals, projects and dreams between chemotherapies by actualising inner potentials such as creativity and imagination as well as relying on media and media-

related practices. The ethos of growth which the cases share, however, was directed towards different goals and combined with artistic intentions as well as spiritual ideas. Karl, a sixty-three-year-old scientist, atheist and enthusiastic amateur filmmaker whose narrative focused mainly on personal achievements, expressed that his last unfulfilled dream was a circumnavigation of the world which he would have captured cinematically in a type of 'emotional life documentary'. He said that the aim was to make this circumnavigation with a so-called 'shrimp trawler' and to shoot footage of nature and the ocean. In doing so, he wanted to continue his cinematic work, 'so what I have now produced as a pure nature film, would have been the idea, on an emotional basis, but with the format of a circumnavigation of the world on such a trawler'. When I asked him about sources of meaning in the difficult situations, he said 'Well, I'm living out my last dream digitally'. As he could no longer keep pace with his progressive ambitions due to the fatal illness, he pursued his film project with the help of the Internet and imagination. He stated that he spends hours in front of the computer, searching for boats, assessing gearboxes and engines, thus planning his trip and artistic project. By attending to his dream, he was able to create a fictional reality that enabled well-being and temporal healing from pain and suffering:

And now I have rediscovered this dream and do nothing else day and night, thanks to the dear Internet and YouTube [...]. And I dream about how beautiful it would be to still be able to experience this dream. With the knowledge that it won't work out anymore; but it gives me incredible pleasure. (Interview: 12 March 2020)

In other cases of the study, the pursuit of artistic projects while dying served the purpose of creating a legacy which would outlive the mortal self. The focus on the possibility of post-physical existence and the imagination of a transcendental future, facilitated by media and material supports, in late modern consumer society has previously been observed (Lee, 2015). Emma, a sixty-eight-year-old photographer, tried to release a photo book while being treated in the palliative care station. It was a great concern of hers that this be done before she dies. Her existence, pre- and post-mortem, was inextricably bound up with her artistic work: 'I hope I can release this book (...). Then I already exist twice' (Interview: 18 November 2020). Art should make her person visible in public before and after death. Her desire was to attain secular immortality through outstanding achievements: 'I'm trying my best to save from my archive whatever can be saved (...) according to the idea "you should have an eternal life and not be forgotten". I know this is somehow foolish but a human desire'. This desire made her act eagerly in the hospital, driven by the hope that her mortal body will be superseded by great pieces of art.

A similar mood of diligence marked other narratives which focused on spiritual development. The endeavour to transform oneself into a transcendent state might be accomplished through art or through a spiritual exercise. Michael, a seventy-eight-year-old teacher, reported 'I'm trying to sort things out from the last years and (...) round off and throw away' (Interview: 27 April 2021). He explained that 'round off' means 'dissolving and connecting in the sense of *via purgativa*', the first step in the threefold path of spiritual development for the union with God, which consists in purification through self-examination (McLaren, 2008). This concern to attain a state of purity, perfection or immortality originates in ancient philosophy and is taken up by Christian asceticism

(Foucault, 1988). In the cultural environments of (late) modern culture, personal catharsis is usually practiced in a small group of spiritual friends who gather to review negative influences on their lives (McLaren, 2008). This was also the case with Michael who used the opportunities between operations, therapies and phases of recreation, created by biomedicine's prolongation of today's dying trajectories (Kellehear, 2017), for spiritual growth. He testified that, having reached the end of his life, he wanted to complete the work of purification and perfection in communicative exchange with others: 'I have gained a lot of experiences in it, in particular in talking to people (. . .) this is something I'm trying to focus on, to round off'. While Emma wanted to achieve secular immortality by transforming life into art, the goal of Michael's ongoing exercise of self-examination through talk was to attain a state of purity. Both practices, however, can be interpreted as forms of transcendence which promote healing in dying. The practices seek to transform the human way of being, which is defective and subject to time, decay and death, drawing on the expressive capacities of art and words and a strong work ethic. In the case of Karl, ongoing artistic project realisation in dying, which enabled temporal healing from suffering, did not, in contrast, involve a reference to a transcendental future.

The spirit of growth, however, which the three cases shared, can also have negative effects on the felt experience of dying. An observed consequence of this spirit was not only a certain unease among the participants, caused by their ambitions, but also a sense of despair and helplessness when illness forced them to give up on the task of self-development. This was particularly evident in Karl's narrative. For him, visions such as the abovementioned circumnavigation of the world were the 'goal' and 'joy' of life, yet with the cancer diagnosis, as he recounted, 'that has crumbled to zero'. In view of the lack of time and his physical limitations, a sense of despair arose. He compared the experience with a 'trapdoor' and emphasised that it is 'the feeling, one can't convey'. Movement and growth, which characterised his individualistic ethos, became overshadowed by the experience of motionlessness, caused by chemotherapies: 'I'm awake for an hour and sleep for an hour. That's what it looks like after the chemo. [. . .]. I lie motionless in the corner'. As previous studies have suggested, in view of the lack of time, persons with an individualistic value orientation one day might realise that their self-project ultimately remains incomplete and 'their fragile attempts at personal meaning left shattered by the brute fact of death' (Mellor & Shilling, 1993, p. 427). An option for those who consider the self the main source of authority out of this dilemma is to transform it into a transcendent state: death is only resisted by those who make themselves immortal through outstanding achievements or who complete the spiritual path. Unending work in the end of life journey can be seen as an offspring of the cultural climate of highly individualistic Western societies.

Self-empowerment and the spirit of sharing

Besides self-actualisation and personal growth, the participants' narratives and practices were informed by the desire to give (public) expression to feelings and emotions. Contrary to nineteenth-century Romanticism, in which suffering and grief were dealt with in private (Walter, 1994), the cases highlight how emotional expressivity in dying has become a (semi) public affair, fostered by the communicative potential of art and the Internet as well as the therapeutic culture of hospice and palliative care. The analysis revealed that my

interlocutors' individual participation in expressive forms of culture at the end of life were informed by self-empowerment strategies, sharing practices and a strive for meaningful connections and community belonging. Sarah, for example, a forty-eight-year-old blogger, used her writing skills to reflect on her personal illness trajectory and to break taboos:

There are posts which express a zest for life. Sure, there also thoughtful moments, when I don't feel well, when I sit at home, when I feel lonely, when I cry, [...]. This is also a part of it. [...]. It's important for me to show every aspect of this illness, also to break the taboo of death. (Interview: 30 April 2021)

Contrary to the assumption that death was silenced in modernity, I think Armstrong (1987) has justifiably argued that since the mid-nineteenth century there has been more discussion on death than ever before. Instead of what has been called 'death denial' – a contested thesis that first arose in the literature between in the period between 1955 and 1985 (Zimmermann & Rodin, 2004) – researchers now speak of death's 'talkativeness' (Nassehi & Saake, 2005).³ However, depending on the social context, talking about death can still be considered a taboo and Sarah's comment indicates that her work aims to fully disclose the experience of illness without feeling ashamed. Since the 'emotional field' (Illouz, 2007, pp. 157–158) of death on the Internet is not controlled by professionals such as psychologists or pastors, which in modernity traditionally governed people's intimate life (Foucault, 1976/1978), those who are directly affected can position themselves as experts in this field and define how illness and death are displayed in public. Sarah, in contrast to other cancer bloggers, who often use a militaristic language of fight, good and evil (Andersson, 2019), takes a reflected approach in this regard. For her, it goes against the grain to accept the media's pornography of cancer death, which normally only pinpoints dead and survivors, winners and losers: 'There exist only two poles: the ones who are dead and the ones who survived. There is nothing in between'. Such ethical imperatives and norms are reinforced by the mediatisation of everyday life and can pose a threat to marginalised groups such as cancer patients. Susan Sontag (1990) has drawn attention to the problematic use of illness as a metaphor and Sarah's comment clearly indicates an awareness of the stigmatisation that this way of reading illness has for those affected. Besides regulating and defining the emotional style and tone of the public debate about illness, Sarah also used her competence and knowledge to help others and establish caring communities. She testified that blogging and writing are more than just forms of self-expression, it is also a way to support other persons in the same situation: 'It is a challenge for me to deal with this illness. And it's my new challenge, my new job, my new business to help others and to be a point of contact for them'.

The wish to display one's own illness in public and to share experiences with an audience, emerged similarly from Emma's narrative. She reported that she has taken selfies on her mobile phone over the last few years which, in a similar vein as Sarah expressed, should document the different emotional tones of the experienced illness trajectory, including the dark moments. She mentioned, for example, that she took a self-portrait after passing out and falling on the floor: 'I had a completely battered face. Because I fainted'. Her interest to pursue this visual 'self-analysis', as she named it, however, was not restricted to a private understanding of her emotions and feelings in the process of dying. She explained that the goal is 'A self-analysis with the option of making an exhibition'. The comment indicates that she aimed to share her bodily harm

and vulnerability with an audience, thus providing an opportunity for others to experience aspects of her illness in relation to the passage of time. Through the visual and verbal representation of their experience of illness, both Emma and Sarah give the experience of illness distinctive 'looks' which can be observed, discussed and consumed by others. At the same time, photographing and blogging are self-empowerment strategies which enable catharsis through verbal and visual self-reflection and aim to establish communicative spaces for knowledge sharing involving different actors. These spaces supplement the traditional therapeutic services of hospice and palliative care in which patients such as Remo, who I cited at the outset of this article, negotiate their emotions and experiences in exchange with professionals such as psychotherapists and pastors. Either way, art, blogging and talking enable persons facing severe illness to get in touch with themselves and their lives, make meaningful connections and to create a sense of belonging through shared vulnerability. The case of Paul, who experienced a long dying trajectory, can elucidate this further. The fifty-nine-year-old suffered from a chronic lung disease and was socially isolated in his last year of life due to the COVID-19 pandemic. To kill time and to get in touch with others, he engaged in photo-sharing. He reported that he took photographs of birds in his backyard and shared them on Facebook: 'I took up the hobby because of my illness, I couldn't do anything anymore (...) because of my dyspnoea, and then I started taking photographs because there was always a crow or a raven in front of the door' (Interview: 22 October 2020). Paul's regular sharing of these pictures together with expressions such as 'Have a nice afternoon and get through the week well' in a Facebook group with an interest in crows laid the foundation for an emotional support network to help him manage the end of life journey. The image-based communication practice of photo-sharing, which in social media environments is fused with video, text and emoticons (Figure 2), was a means to create and sustain relationships while dying. When Paul commented on his poor condition, for example, people texted back quickly with messages such as 'Get well soon' and 'I'm very sorry. Don't lose hope' (Figure 3). In the communicative interactions, weak and strong attachments emerged and vulnerability was thus shared and mitigated. Paul's photo-sharing indicates a form of 'networked individualism' (Castells, 2001, p. 129) which establishes social contact in dying based on personal interests and proactive actions.

Another type of community with loose boundaries and selective participation which my interlocuters relied on to deal with end of life issues, were self-helps groups. In contrast to the community Paul engaged in, which was based on a shared interest in birds, peer-to-peer relationships of people undergoing similar experiences of illness were of particular importance in this respect. Anna, a fifty-four-year-old teacher, who initiated a peer-to-peer support network for cancer patients, expressed that she needs to talk to people in the same situation who have a common language: 'As a person affected by cancer, I really feel the urge to talk to people in the same situation. There are some things that only affected persons can understand [...].' (Interview: 2 September 2021). Creating networks for sharing knowledge with others who talk the same language and can understand the pain and suffering one is going through was also an ambition of Sarah's work. By telling her own story of illness, she aimed at helping others in the same situation: 'And I tell my story, but it doesn't end there. I want to share what I've learned and pass something on to other people. [...]. I also created an online self-help group for women with metastatic cancer'. Anna, Emma, Paul and Sarah all seemed to share the idea that

Figure 2. Screenshot of one of Paul's Facebook postings. Posted on 9 March 2020.

managing the end of life journey is both something that is to be under one's control and something that has to be achieved with the help of others. The way in which this is accomplished seems consciously and autonomously chosen by each of them on the basis of their individual capacities, interests and needs. At the same time, the cases confirm the observation that expressive subjectivity is always reliant on a social context in which the expressed experiences and feelings resonate (Bellah et al., 1996). Relating to oneself and one's potential to cope with dying is simultaneously embedded in social relationships and attachments which emerge in both offline and online contexts and in the mutual exchange with professionals, peers and strangers. Self-empowerment, sharing,

express that she needs silence and privacy in dying, partly because she seemed to feel ashamed of it, partly because retreat fitted her contemplative lifestyle. For her, self-chosen solitude had a positive quality and was not to be confused with the negative emotion of loneliness, which many older people experience due to the weakening of social ties (Elias, 1982/2001; Sjöberg et al., 2018). Solitude and silence brought peace and were something relaxing in her end of life journey. This quality was also highlighted by Marta, an eighty-year-old music therapist, who enjoyed doing nothing and watching out of the window: 'I personally often just lie in bed. (...) Just do nothing. I'm also a person of silence. (...) Music and silence go together. [...] I'm sitting in the chair and look into the distance, it's so beautiful' (Interview: 24 November 2020). Francine's and Marta's stories highlight that the blank between the words should be noted and respected. 'Being silent' was an integral part of Saunders' revolutionary patient-centred approach to terminal care (Saunders, 2003), but today sometimes seems to be overlooked in the wake of the triumph of therapeutic culture. Karl also highlighted the quality of remaining silent. He recounted that, instead of talking to psychologists or pastors, he often meets an old friend. His sheer presence would do him good: 'He doesn't ask. He is just here. [...] That helps me the most'. However, these narratives reveal an interdependency of the values of expression and silence as well as the desire for both company and solitude. This combination of values illuminates another important aspect of 'being expressive' at the end of life and emphasises the importance of paying attention to the words left unsaid and unseen, aspects by which the things heard and seen in the ethnographic fieldwork take on their meaning.

Discussion and conclusion

The results of this study show that many of the values and ideas, which according to Walter (1994) are catch-phrases of 'neo-modern death', characterise the expressive endeavours of the studied individuals. These catch-phrases are: talk, expression of emotion, self-help groups, self-focus, growth, autonomy and choice. The findings highlight that these values are lived out individually by engaging in different expressive practices and media and overlap with what Walter considers traditional and modern ideas such as belonging, community and silence. The empirical connections between Walter's ideal types and the expressive endeavours of the participants, which I illuminated in the analysis and in many cases consist of a crisscrossing between the types, demonstrate that there exists no ideal model for dying. Both the romanticised narrative of the 'good' pre-modern death in the bosom of one's own family (Ariès, 1976) and the common distinction between a 'bad' modern and a 'good' neo-modern death, as fostered by the modern hospice movement, should be critically examined in the light of the findings of this study. Silence and retreat from the attention of the public are not necessarily an indicator of a repression of death and the 'negative side of discourse' (Armstrong, 1987, p. 651), but, as the discussed examples highlight, have positive qualities which enhance emotional well-being in dying. In addition, the question arises how identified features of the participants' expressive endeavours such as sharing and community participation can be illuminated and situated within the framework of Walter's ideal types. It can be questioned whether and to what extent the observed search for belonging is a feature

of 'traditional death' or rather expresses a universal need when it comes to existential issues. Scholars like Amanda Lagerkvist (2014) argue that media cultures in the digital age and people's practices therein to cope with grief and suffering retain an 'existential quest for *communitas*' (p. 205). Following Viktor Turner (1969), Lagerkvist (2014) claims that '*communitas* is a sense of profound and inspired comradeship' (p. 214), emerging spontaneously at different times and locations. Whether this quest for *communitas* in the confrontation with death is a fact about life which is an inescapable truth of being human can obviously not be answered based on the findings of an ethnographic study. However, the results point to the current trend of connectivity and demonstrate how proactive actions of dying persons and their participation in loose-knit communities provide a sense of belonging through shared vulnerability. Sharing information related to illness and expression of feelings provide a means to maintain social relationships in dying, thus alleviating loneliness and isolation, as, for example, Paul's practice of photo-sharing during the pandemic illustrates. In this regard, the findings show that within current Western societies, digital technologies have enabled the creation of new social contexts for dealing with death, which co-exist with institutional and private settings of support and care. One possible reading of this development is that the social structures and communicative potentials of virtual worlds and the Internet accommodate an individualistic lifestyle at the end of life as they offer the possibility to mix self-empowerment and individual forms of expression with a sense of belonging and community.

Given the nearly thirty years which have passed since Walter's (1994) book was published, it is not surprising that the ideal types need to be revised and expanded. In light of the empirical findings of this study, I propose to situate neo-modern death within the developments of digital prosumerism. The term 'prosumption' refers to the combination of production and consumption (Ritzer et al., 2012), which is a popular practice in Internet cultures where people share created images, memes, videos etc. and concurrently consume the content of other users. Walter himself and other studies have highlighted the increasing relevance of digital technologies for meaning making at the end of life (Lagerkvist, 2019; Rains, 2018; Walter, 2020; Walter et al., 2012). The analysis revealed that prosumers facing death influence the emotional style and tone of the public debate about illness and contribute to our understanding of dying by sharing their experiences and struggles. Practices such as blogging and photo-sharing are used for destigmatisation and empowerment as well as to create audiences for one's own fight with loneliness, isolation and existential insecurity. In exchange with different groups and facilitated by a variety of (digital) media, experiences and emotions in dying are negotiated and (co) created as part of collective processes of sharing and communication. In the studied cases, the relational configurations out of which experiences and emotions develop (Döveling et al., 2018) involved various actors, material objects, such as artwork and photographs, and communicative practices. Both the characteristics and qualities of the media and the prevailing cultural conditions along with palliative treatments structure the experience of dying as a social process which contains, as the results show, recurring patterns among patients with different worldviews. The examined participation in forms of expressive culture at the end of life is strongly influenced by individualistic values as well as the rise of digital media. Catch-phrases to be added to Walter's ideal type of neo-modern death based on the social developments in networked society and the findings of this study thus are: connectivity, digital coping and digital prosumerism.

Notes

1. The names of all participants are pseudonyms. Details such as names of places and third parties that could lead to identification of the informants were removed from the article. The project was reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich (Declaration of Competence BASEC-No. Req-2019-00221, Cantonal Ethics Committee Zurich, Switzerland). Written or oral informed consent was obtained from all participants.
2. Art therapy as a widespread practice in palliative care is not covered in this article. A considerable amount of literature has been published on this topic (Butchers et al., 2008; La Cour et al., 2007; Pratt & Wood, 2015).
3. The proliferation of 'Death Cafes' across the globe can be seen as an indicator of this development.

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